

ARTISTIC EXPRESSION OF FEMALE PSYCHOLOGY IN THE DRAMAS OF USMON AZIM

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Abstract: This thesis discusses the portrayal of female characters and the depiction of their inner psychology in the dramatic works of Usmon Azim, one of the prominent representatives of contemporary Uzbek literature. The drama "A Single Step" (Bir qadam yo'l) has been selected as the primary object of analysis.

Keywords: drama, artistry, artistic depiction, character, psychological portrayal.

Introduction

In literary criticism, the issue of psychologism is based on the artistic depiction of the hero's inner world, mental state, feelings, thoughts, and emotions. This concept manifests through two methods: explicit (direct) and implicit (indirect) description. Literary scholar Dilmurod Quronov explains these two concepts in his textbook "Foundations of Literary Theory": "A writer can describe a character's psychology directly or indirectly. The manifestation of a character's thoughts and feelings in the form of 'inner monologue,' 'stream of consciousness,' or through the author's narration is considered a direct form of psychological description. The revelation of a character's psyche through their actions, speech, facial expressions (mimicry), and physiological changes is an indirect psychological description" [1.72]. To support his views, the scholar cites the following example: "Otabek leaned against the wall as if stunned; the thrones, crowns, khans, and beks, which held some meaning here, were worthless in his eyes... Truth be told, he had entered a strange state; his body was dry and sensationless..." [1.70]. In this passage from the novel "Days Gone By" (O'tkan kunlar), the author attempts to reveal the psychological state of his hero directly through his thoughts.

Furthermore, one can observe the following passage from the novel "Night and Day" (Kecha va kunduz): "...She only heard Qumri's words—the last words: 'one of them is our own cart-driver...' Her heart fluttered... she immediately turned and looked outside. The fluttering of her heart did not subside. Her lips began to tremble..." [1.72].

Usmon Azim demonstrated unique skill in depicting characters, their feelings, experiences, and spiritual sufferings in his dramas. Among many dramatic works such as "In the Lands Where the Dawn Breaks" (Tong otgan taraflarda), "Nightless Days" (Kunduzsiz kechalar), and "Love" (Sevgi), his work titled "A Single Step" (Bir qadam yo'l) stands out significantly.

In the drama "A Single Step," the author's skill in depicting human psychology is clearly visible in the interpretation of female figures. Women play a vital role in the development of the plot and the expression of artistic conflict.

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For a woman, the highest praise is a single kind word and a bit of affection from her spouse. There can be no greater happiness in the world! For Saodat, even a single sentence from her husband Jo'ra—"You are a good woman... Don't cry, why are you crying!" [2.341]—was enough. Although a simple village chairman could not say more flamboyant words, for his wife, this meant the whole world. His encouragement naturally affected the woman's psychological state and caused a change in the relationship between the characters.

Her sister-in-law Beg'am is the complete opposite of Saodat. For her, every word, praise, or endearment from her husband Shokir pierces her heart like an arrow and wounds her; she lives only for her child Isroil, breathes only for him, and follows Shokir only for his sake. The writer effectively used psychological imagery to express the character's states:

Shokir: Beg'am, why are your eyes red? Have you been crying? **Beg'am:** Have I been crying?! **Shokir:** Why are you crying? **Beg'am:** When I married you, I took it upon myself to cry for a lifetime. **Shokir:** Beg'am, I love you. But for twenty years, you have looked at me as if looking at an enemy. You fight a secret war with me. You have your own boundaries. You don't even let me near that place [2.369].

Here, the writer, based on the nature of the dramatic work, expressed the mental states of the characters through their speech. That is, Beg'am's red eyes and her state of crying are understood through Shokir's speech. Beg'am's own speech also reveals the result of intense spiritual suffering. Therefore, in these descriptions, the writer expressed the changes in the character's psychology based on the indirect method of description.

In another part of the work, Beg'am says to her sister-in-law Saodat: "Everyone has their own hell in this world, sister-in-law, just pray to God!" [2.348]. Her inner suffering is evident in these words. Even though she loved someone else before, she remains faithful to her husband and family, never even thinking of betrayal.

The character of Salima in the drama is also depicted in the grip of suffering. Salima says to Qosim: "I lost my shame and modesty because of you! It's been nine years—I have no peace! I gave up everything for you! I brought shame to my parents! I abandoned my family! I divorced my husband! Here I am, following you, taking the disgrace upon myself! I beg you, I am about to break, take me before I crumble! If you won't take me as a wife, take me as a concubine! Let me be your servant!" [2.364]. Through this monological speech (addressed to Qosim), the writer vividly reflected the experiences in her heart. It is clear that the character underwent intense psychological distress. At this point, it can be said that in a dramatic work, the monologue is an important tool for bringing out the inner world of the character. This is because the character speaks to themselves in moments of intense internal conflict, revealing sorrows to the reader or audience that they cannot tell anyone else. This serves as an example of the indirect method of expressing psychological imagery, as the writer reveals the character's inner feelings through their speech.

In addition, Usmon Azim created images of faithful, resilient, and strong-willed women such as Soliha in "Nightless Days," Zarifa in "The Life of the Writer," and Tongyorug' and Kunyorug' in "In the Lands Where the Dawn Breaks," utilizing psychologism effectively in their depiction.

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It can be observed that the possibilities for depicting a character's psychology in a dramatic work are vast. In his drama "A Single Step," Usmon Azim followed a unique path in describing female psychology. It is evident that the author succeeded in opening the characters more deeply by resorting mostly to the indirect method of psychological description.

Conclusion

In conclusion, one of the important aspects that ensured the artistic perfection of the dramas created by Usmon Azim is visible in his skill in depicting the character and psychology of the personages. The writer pays great attention to the depiction of the inner world alongside the speech and actions of his heroes. As a result, the poignancy of the works increases, attracting the attention of readers and viewers. As it is said, "words are weightier with proof," and the following thoughts from Izzat Sul-ton's book "Theory of Literature" are a clear testament to this conclusion: "In works of fiction, which consist of human studies, we witness people being depicted with various levels of detail and depth" [3.103].

List of used literature:

1. Quronov D. Foundations of Literary Theory. – Tashkent: Innovatsiya-ziyo, 2020. – pp. 70, 72.
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3. Izzat Sul-ton. Theory of Literature. – Tashkent: "O'qituvchi" Publishing House, 2005. p. 103.